

‘No weapon could bite him’ – Magic weapons and armour in the middle ages

Magic weapons and armour are things we usually associate with the realms of myth or fantasy rather than history. And yet, in semi-historical and even historical sources throughout the medieval period we find accounts of magic weapons which bring down foes or inspire comrades, or of shields and armour which protect the wearer no matter what they faced. What is more, it is clear that there is a historical reality at play in such mythological accounts and we can see a clear development of how mundane equipment came to be considered magical.

‘I shall call thee ...’ The tradition of named weapons

The tradition of named weapons is well known – Siegfried’s sword Balmung (or Nothung), Thor’s hammer Mjölfnir, Arthur’s Excalibur, or Attila’s ‘Sword of Mars’ (Jordanes *Getica* 35) and many, many others. As can be seen in these examples we can easily transition from myth to semi-historical, and into historical characters, all of whom had named weapons. Indeed, the history of named weapons dates back to antiquity and there are literally hundreds of them across all cultures where swords, and any other weapon type you care to name, were used: Scandanavian, Near Eastern, Indian, South-East Asian, Greek and Roman, Germanic and Celtic. In a similar vein, the history of named ships is an old one and one which continues today. In the medieval period we have Arthur’s ship, with the same name as his shield, Prydwen (meaning ‘fair-face’), and the Norse god Baldur’s ship Hringhorni, the greatest of all ships, and others. Some of the ideas behind ship names, luck and feminine identities especially, can be seen in the middle ages and they remain in place.

Some named weapon traditions do indeed come from a later period: Julius Caesar’s sword, called *Crocea Mors* (‘Yellow Death’), comes from Geoffrey of Monmouth in the 12th century (and not earlier). According to Geoffrey, it was acquired by the British prince Nennius in single combat with Caesar (*History of the Kings of Britain* 4.3-4). Elsewhere in the Welsh Annals it is called ‘Red Death’ or ‘Grey Death’; the magic sword killed if it inflicted even the smallest wound.

A word should be said here about my use of the word ‘magic’ as I am using it to refer to weapons across a range of times, cultures and religious beliefs. Here ‘magic’ should simply be understood as a weapon, shield or armour which was considered to possess special qualities outside of the norm of a weapon or piece of equipment of that type.

Of course, we have archaeological finds of actual inscribed swords, scabbards (and spearheads too) from the 3rd to the 11th centuries at least. Some of these are the names of the man who made the blade such as the numerous *Ulfberht* swords. This is still an important tradition in the vein of figures like Weyland the Smith. Other blades seem to have owner's name inscribed. There are makers' marks too, and magical stamps and inscriptions (such as a boar stamp or the complete Runic *futhorc*) but there are also named weapons. Many of these inscriptions are unclear and their interpretation debated. The names are intriguing in themselves – 'famous one', 'increase to pain'; others suggest elements like 'test', 'assailant', 'harm' or speed ('rushing', 'whirring'). Weapon names were a very personal thing and it should be no surprise that their interpretation is difficult, but these actual examples bear out that weapon-naming was not just a literary or a mythological tradition. It should also be noted that swords were most commonly named on the tang of the blade where the name could be seen in combat. Runes and symbols were more commonly inscribed on the hilt (guard or pommel) or scabbard, although there are hilt inscriptions too.

In the *Mabinogion* story *How Culhwch won Olwen*, king Arthur names more than just his sword: 'my sword Caledvwlch, my spear Rhongomyniad, my shield Wynebgwrthucher, my knife Carnwennan.' Layamon's *Brut* names Arthur's helmet (which had been his father Uther's) as Goswhit. Arthur's shield is possibly the first named magic armour in his tradition, named before any weapon of his is introduced. The *Annales Cambriae* name the shield at the battle of Badon in the year 516 – (although this involves the confusion of the Welsh for 'shoulders' to be understood for 'shield'): 'Arthur carried the Cross of Our Lord Jesus Christ for three days and three nights on his shoulders.' The author Nennius records (56) that the shield depicting the Virgin Mary was carried at the battle of Gunnion Fort, not Badon Hill.

A folk-tale from the Isle of Man tells of Culann manufacturing a sword, spear and shield for Conchobar, future King of Ulster. Conchobar had consulted the Oracle at Clogher and was told to go to Man and have the weapons made. The story also tells of a mermaid, captured by Conchobar, who told him to have her image and name 'Teeval, the Princess of the Ocean' inscribed on the shield. She promised that if he looked upon the image before battle and invoked her name the strength of his enemies would diminish while his and his companions' would increase proportionately. The shield was made in this way and Conchobar thereafter saw nothing but success. The idea of a shield blazon having special powers goes back to ancient Greece at least and

inspirational or fear-inspiring shield designs continued in the Roman, and then into medieval, period.

Inspiration

Magic weapons could also inspire men around them. We need look no further than the discovery of the Holy Lance (which had pierced Christ's side) in Antioch on June 14, 1098 and the effect it had on the hard-pressed Crusaders in the city (*Gesta Francorum* 9.25): 'their spirits revived at once.' When the army went to battle before the walls, the lance went with them, carried by the bishop of Le Puy (9.39), and they were victorious. Raymond of Aguilers' account is even more inspired than the anonymous author of the *Gesta*. Raymond was one of the men sent to find the Lance: 'I, Raymond, author of this book, kissed the point of the lance as it barely protruded from the ground. I cannot relate the happiness and rejoicing which filled Antioch.' The magic protection the lance offered during the battle is recounted by Raymond: 'Superior in numbers, they neither wounded anyone nor shot arrows against us, no doubt because of the protection of the Holy Lance. I was both a witness to these events and bearer of the Holy Lance.' Anna Comnena names it as the Holy Nail (since the relic of the Holy Lance was supposed to be already in Constantinople!) We might be sceptical of the discovery of such a relic (although belief in relics persists to this day) but what was important for the crusaders was their belief that they had found the Lance and the inspiration it produced. A similar idea of inspiration can be seen in the military standards of medieval armies, several of which were considered magical, whether they bore the cross, the Oriflamme or the raven. This in many ways reflected the importance of military standards reaching back in to the Roman period (King Arthur's *draco* standard was probably based on a roman cavalry pennant).

Magical armour

We have several accounts of magic armour from antiquity onwards, such as that made for Achilles by the god Hephaestus, god of the forge (*Iliad* 18.478-608). Several sets of armour like these, and other, later sets, like the armour made for Beowulf by Weyland the Smith, are not given any specific magical properties – their magic lies in their undoubted quality, assured by the smith who made them. Others have a quality implied in who their owner was – the shield of El Cid or his two named swords, Tizona and Colada, for instance. Now, you might argue that most of these examples are mythological and therefore not strictly historical but several vital aspects of military culture survive in mythology and the historical record is revealed via these examples. The idea of

stripping a defeated foe (present throughout medieval warfare) was not only a way of obtaining wealth. To have taken the sword, armour or shield of a prominent warrior would enhance your reputation on the battlefield (something the poet expresses in *The Battle of Maldon*, lines 159-161). And the qualities assumed to belong to those items came from whose they had been and how skilled the present owner needed to be in order to have got them. This can also be seen, in part, in cultures where a victorious warrior absorbed the skills of his defeated opponent.

Invisibility Cloaks?!

There are some magic armour traditions which span cultures and time – in the *Nibelungenlied* (3,7), Siegfried obtains a cloak which renders him invisible. In Greek mythology, Hades had a helmet which made him invisible, made for him by the Cyclopes. This helmet was worn by various figures including Athena (*Iliad* 5.844), Hermes and Perseus (who was given them by Athena in some versions of the Persues/Gorgon myth). Another invisibility cloak is attributed to Arthur (the *Llen Arthyr yng Nghernyw* or ‘Mantle of Arthur in Cornwall’), one of the *Thirteen Treasures of the Island of Britain*, a Welsh text from the 15th century. Again, we might pour scorn on this idea as mythology (or Harry Potter) but in the ancient world, for instance, the power of Alexander the Great’s cloak was considered real – Pompey the Great wore it in his triumph (Appian *Mithridatic Wars* 24.117) almost three hundred years later. The cloak-like *aegis* of Zeus is another powerful mantle. We also need to consider the power of such ‘stories.’ We may laugh at them, or at those who believe them, but belief in stories of the Grail or the clear inspiring power of the discovery of the Holy Lance at Antioch for instance were decidedly real. Fear of the magical qualities of the Viking berserker were also very real. And the stories of heroes’ accoutrement whether they be Beowulf, El Cid or Roland inspired generations. Weapons also took on power in both myth and history based on ‘their’ deeds; who they had killed and fought with or what they meant – the sword in the stone and the sword in the tree of the *Völsung Saga* are clear examples.

King Arthur and his Knights

Many ‘magical’ items belong to the stories of Arthur and his knights although their genesis is more complicated. Sir Percival had the shield of Joseph of Arimathea, Gawain had the shield of Judas Maccabeus, Galahad the Shield of king Evalach and the knights also had named swords and lances. These were all tied to a Christian tradition (the shield of Evalach had had a cross drawn on it by Joseph of Arimathea in his own blood and Joseph had also brought weapons with him). One of

the most difficult figures to decipher and interpret in the Arthurian tradition is the Green Knight. For our purposes, across the three poems where he originally appears (*Sir Gawain and the Green Knight* from the 14th century, *The Greene Knight* from around 1500 and *King Arthur and King Cornwall* from slightly later), he is sent to test the abilities and loyalty of Arthur's knights. In the *Sir Gawain* poem, he wears no armour but is all green including his hair and skin (and is protected from harm) but in *The Greene Knight* he has magical green armour. There are several figures upon whom the Green Knight could have been based but, importantly for us, there seem to be several historical figures who may have inspired or emulated him or the idea of him. The *Continuation of William of Tyre* (63) has a Green Knight, the Spaniard Sancho Martin, who led sorties from Tyre in 1197, and there are other green-clad knights in stories of Saladin (which all pre-date the Green Knight poems). This figure may have connections with the Green Man/al-Khidr figure from the *Quran* (Sura 18.65-82), sent to test Moses (and so perhaps the figure was also sent to test Saladin, not to mention Arthur) or the motif of the Green Man, popular in medieval art.

Ragnar Loðbrok and the Norse tradition

In the stories of Ragnar Loðbrok we find several explanations of his nickname 'hairy-breeches' as being related to a special armour which would protect him from a serpent/dragon's bite. Explanations of what this armour was vary – from frozen lambs' wool to boiled animal skin with the hair on the outside. It is interesting that these explanations take on a relatively mundane, practical and plausible explanation of their 'magical' quality. Of course, in the *Nibelungenlied* (chapter 3), Siegfried famously bathed in the blood of a dragon to gain similar protection:

‘This hero slew a dragon and bathed in its blood, from which his skin grew horny
so that no weapon will bite it, as has been shown time and time again.

Siegfried's magical armour is also linked to Achilles' magical protection when he was dipped in the river Styx by his mother, Thetis, holding him by the ankle and thus creating his literal Achilles' heel (Statius *Achilleid* 1.133-135). Siegfried's weak point was where a leaf fell 'between his shoulder-blades' (*Nibelungenlied*, chapter 3, 15).

The phrase that no weapon could 'bite' him recalls similar phrases used of the Viking *berserker* who were also considered to have magical protection. The sagas are full of such men (they tend to prove mortal enough) but the terminology which surrounds them suggests that they, and their enemies, thought themselves magically protected. Their origins are disputed and agreement cannot

be reached on whether they are named after the idea that they were ‘unarmoured’ or ‘in shirt only’ (the meaning of *berserke* in Swedish). Others have them in a bear skin to distinguish them from the *ulfbedner* who wore wolf skins, and some consider these the same as berserkers. In *Grettir’s Saga* (2) at the battle of Hafrsfjord, the berserkers wore wolf-skins: ‘no iron could hurt them, and when they charged nothing could withstand them.’ This, of course does not delve into the animalistic battle rage aspect of the berserker, not to mention the belief that they could shape-shift into animal form. These topics are complex and deserve a fuller, independent, treatment. Other figures from medieval warfare supposedly fought naked such as the Irish according to Gerald of Wales.

In the *Havamal* (*Sayings of the High One*) Odin has several spells where he can either blunt the blades, protect the skin or cause several other afflictions to his enemies. *Havamal* 148 speaks of a spell ‘which fetters my enemy; the edges of my foes I can blunt, neither weapon nor club will bite for them.’ And 156: ‘if I have to lead loyal friends into battle; under the shields I chant, and they journey inviolate, safely into battle, safely from the battle, safely they come everywhere.’ In the context of Siegfried and Ragnar, *Havamal* 158 seems most pertinent: ‘if I shall pour water over a young warrior: he will not fall though he goes into battle, before swords he will not sink.’

These spells come together with the berserker in the *Ynglinga Saga* (6) where they are defined:

Odin could make his enemies in battle blind, or deaf, or terror-struck, and their weapons so blunt that they could cut no more than a willow wand; on the other hand, his men rushed forward without armour, and were as mad as dogs or wolves, bit their shields, were as strong as bears or wild bulls, and killed people at a blow, but neither fire nor iron told upon themselves.

This account has similarities to the report of the qualities of the Holy Lance and other similar items. Christian prayers for protection, strength and the disabling of enemies’ abilities are also remarkably similar. There is the magical protection offered to the berserker too but what is surprising is the remarkable accounts we have of actual attempts at special armour in the Viking tradition. One thing to note is that they are all suggested as practical solutions to magic armour (and are all cheaper alternatives to metal armour). The *Gesta Herwardi* 11 records that rebels in Zeeland had felt cloaks impregnated with resin or pitch to make them impenetrable. Hereward also had a ‘famous sword’ which had done great deeds, that he obtained in single combat (chapter 3). In *Ragnars Saga* (2), his clothes are made of animal hide with the hair on the outside, boiled in pitch and then rolled in sand. Saxo (*Gesta Danorum* 9.252) recounts that Ragnar ‘begged from his

nurse a woollen cloak and some very shaggy thigh-coverings, with which he could subdue the serpents' bites. He dressed himself like this believing that such clothing, cushioned with hair, would act as protection and at the same time be flexible enough to allow nimble movement. When his ship touched the Swedish coast, the weather was freezing; he intentionally threw himself into the waters then exposed his soaking garments to be stiffened by the cold, so that they would become even less penetrable.'

The saga version would seem to have more practical effect, rationalising the stories of myth. A Transylvanian folk-tale of a dragon-slayer also has the hero don a lambskin coat and jump into an icy river so that the frozen wool would grant him protection. All of these might seem naïve and unbelievable but in 1977 John McPhee published an account of his travels in Alaska (*Coming into the Country* (New York, 1977), page 67). He recounted the story that male grizzly bears venturing out in winter would find a patch of open water in an otherwise frozen river, would wet their fur and then roll in the snow. The fur would thus acquire a thick ice-plate: 'arrows broke against the armouring ice, and it can be heavy enough to stop a bullet.' This is, according to McPhee, was the feared 'winter bear' of the Eskimo and this story seems to give credence to the saga version. We therefore see a plausible practical armour which could quite easily be interpreted or recorded as 'magical'.

More Magical Armour

Other examples of magic armour occur in the medieval period too – in the Persian epic the *Shahnameh*, Esfandiyar was given armour from heaven by the prophet Zoroaster which made him invincible. He also bathed in a pool of invincibility (like Siegfried and Achilles, but Esfandiyar's eyes were his vulnerable point since he closed them when he immersed himself – and his eyes proved to be his 'Achilles' heel' when he was killed by Rostam who also had his share of magical equipment). The god Baldur was only vulnerable to a spear made of mistletoe (*Gylfaginning* 49) thrown by the blind Hod after Loki's interference. In Saxo Grammaticus' historicized version of the same story in the *Gesta Danorum* 3.64-69, Balderus could not be harmed by steel and he was eventually killed by a combination of poison, a bracelet of strength, and a belt which allowed Høther to plunge a magic sword into Balderus' side. Høther had also been given an 'impenetrable coat' and earlier (3.66) he wore a 'sword-proof tunic'.

According to French historian Marion Melville, the red cross of the Knights Templar was intended to act as a shield (*La Vie des Templiers* (Paris, 1951), page 92). This red cross became associated with Saint George, the warrior saint, (who also wielded named weapons) during the second crusade although its genesis is complicated; it is also associated with Genoa and Aragon. This protection is a rather literal interpretation of the idea expressed later in the 15th century by Thomas à Kempis: ‘in the Cross is protection against our enemies’ (*The Imitation of Christ* 2.12.2) but the idea of a symbol on a surcoat (or shield) which would protect the wearer is not that far removed from the magical shields and armour we have seen here.

Final Thoughts

The ideas touched upon here are complex and tied inextricably to belief and myth but there is enough history to show that tales of magical weapons and armour may very well have their origins in the weapons and armour of actual individuals involved in real events.

Further Reading

H. R. Ellis Davidson *The Sword in Anglo-Saxon England* (Woodbridge, 1962).

Paddy Griffith *The Viking Art of War* (London, 1995).

A. H. Krappe ‘Sur un épisode de la saga de Ragnar Lodbrók’ *Acta Philologica Scandinavica* 15 (1941-2), 326-338.

N. Lukman ‘Ragnarr Loðbrók, Sigifrid, and the Saints of Flanders’, *Medieval Scandinavia* 9 (1976), 7-50.

John McPhee *Coming into the Country* (New York, 1977)

E. Ploss *Siegfried-Sigurd der Drachenkämpfer* (Cologne, 1966).

Martina Sprague *Norse Warfare* (New York, 2007).

Michael Wild’s page http://www.geocities.ws/dagonet_uk/